

EDUCATIONAL SIGNIFICANCE OF VIDEO MATERIALS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract. *The article devoted to the effective use of the video materials in teaching English. It states that the use of the video materials in teaching English develops the learners' language skills.*

Keywords: *video materials, modern technology, multimedia resources.*

Nowadays, videos play an important role in education. The use of videos can facilitate the students their learning activities because they can have different learning experiences. It claimed: “when a person has images, actions, goals, and dialogues to attach to words, they have an embodied understanding of those words.” As a result, films assist learners in seeing language embodied by supplying them with images [Gee and Hayes 2011, p.116].

Videos could boost students' learning experiences by enriching their knowledge of the language in use, improving their cross-cultural understanding, developing their creativity, and raising their enthusiasm to learn. Videos may give extra benefits for learners, such as students could not only hear but also see the facial emotions and movements when they observed the language in use. Videos could be considered as a means of stimulating reading, acquiring knowledge and activating the memory of students; they also may enhance students' understanding and discussion skills. Since the 1990s up till the present time, when video become widely available as a teaching resource, English foreign language researchers and educators [Altman R., 1989; Allan M., 1985; Wang V.C., 211; Harmer J., 2001; Berk, R. A., 2009] have asserted the importance of incorporating video material in the learning of language. Some of educators believe that “videos expose students to authentic materials and to voices, dialects, and registers other than the teacher's and provide cultural contexts for that foreign language; Furthermore, videos are thought to provide more motivation and interest to English foreign language students.

Broady claimed that because of video learners have a motivation to communicate with each other and with the teacher [Broady E., 1996, p.18]. Also Altman claims to have developed a new “pedagogy” or “methodology” based on video. Moreover; Altman like to use video because video can support any grammatical or cultural topic as well as contextualize grammar and vocabulary by embedding language in a relatively natural context. For this reason, authentic videos are preferred by Altman [Altman R., 1989].

According to Stempleski and Tomalin, authentic videos are “a rich and exciting source of video software for EFL/ESL classes” [Stempleski and Tomalin, 1990, p. 83].

Chung and Huang acquiesce to the previous quote by clearly stating that: “As more complete video instructional packages are made available to foreign language teacher, they search for ways to make students' learning experience more active and interesting, similar to those that occur in the real world” [Chung J.M. and Huang S.C., 1998, p. 554].

Videos bring language in the context of life in realistic settings to the classroom. Also videos are so close to language reality-containing visual as well as audible cues. In addition to; it is an excellent medium for use in the language classroom. Video offers foreign language learners a chance to improve their ability to understand comprehension input course.

According to the deputy director of Britain's Open University Margaret Johnson; "I think always to listen and to see something at the same time is useful, particularly if some students find it easier to learn through visual things and other students find it easier to learn through hearing. If you can get the combination of the two then is particularly helpful" [Acklam R. and Robertson C., 2000, p. 128].

In addition to, the learners who are studying English in a non-English speaking setting, it is very important to experience real communicative situations in which they will learn how to express their own views and opinions, and to develop their oral fluency and accuracy which are very essential for the success of FL communication. The choice of video techniques and materials from teaching aids due to the effectiveness in developing speaking skills and as a motivating factor in improving communication ability comes from the belief that video techniques are usually conceivable in a format that holds the interest of the most students. Because, they interest in technology in teaching process since we are in 21 century. The use of technology in education is not the question. The real question is how to harvest the power of technology to meet the challenges of the 21st century and make education relevant, responsive, and effective for the students.

Generally, videos could be defined as a technique used to capture, record, process, transmit and reproduce a series of images that represent a moving scene. According to Gee and Hayes videos were defined as texts that incorporate various methods, like words, images, and sounds [Gee and Hayes 2011].

In addition, "video is defined here as digitally recorded content that has sound and motion that can be stored or delivered live and can be streamed to a variety of devices. It may or may not have the lecturer visible and can include an animated film, or a demonstration" [Woolfitt Z., 2015, p.4].

In both cases, whether the videos are recorded or live, they had sound and motion that may be stored or streamed to a number of devices. Videos may play a leading role in teaching and learning a foreign language. Video is at best defined as the selection and sequence of messages in an audio-visual context. By putting the knowledge in a real-life setting, video techniques assisted learners in grasping the information. Therefore, educators observe that it is crucial to consider the perceptions of technology adopters towards the innovation. The opinion of the users towards the technology tool will determine the success of implementation. Videos work well when teachers favour the new technologies to enhance conventional methods, they will be willing or unable to use them meaningfully. It is recommended that teachers need support and training to utilize technology into their lessons.

A research on teachers perceptions on the utilization of YouTube videos in an English language learning in **Australian National University in Canberra** showed that teachers think that YouTube can motivate students and described the videos as interesting or attractive. Some teachers associated the attractiveness of YouTube to its multimodality, which also helps cater for diversity in the classroom. Students who are visually inclined were able to learn and recall better. Teachers think that YouTube

videos can help learners acquire language skills with ease. Teachers however felt that they have a challenge in getting the appropriate videos. They also could not use the interactive nature of YouTube by commenting on the video online because of lack of familiarity with the same [Diane Larsen-Freeman and Marti Anderson, 2015, p.257].

Perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are two major determinants of a consumer's acceptance of a technology. Perceived usefulness in this study refers to how teachers perceive YouTube videos to support their teaching. If a video clip can help a teacher to explain a complex concept easily there is a likelihood that he/she will use it again. Perceived ease of use refers to the user's perception of amount of the effort necessary for using the system. Language teachers can utilize resources from YouTube if they believe that they can support realization of the objectives of the lesson.

YouTube resources can be a valuable teaching material that can motivate learners as well as enhance performance. However, teachers experiences using the videos can affect their willingness to use this resource in class. If teachers perceive the videos as useful, user friendly and accessible then there is a like hood that they will use them to teach. Some teachers view technology as time consuming. It is useful that if teachers are exposed to lessons fully designed with ICT, then they will be encouraged to implement the same. This research sought to find out how the training on using internet resources was done and if the teachers have enough skills to integrate videos in the lesson.

We should also note that new digital technologies are being used to teach, some teachers do not use them because of their attitude and institutional factors. Most teachers prefer traditional teaching methods to teach speaking skills like pronunciation. According to our research studies, it is necessary to note the usefulness of these technologies so that they become appealing to the teachers.

We also should discuss the importance of using methods that cater for different learning styles. These include visual, auditory, kinesthetic and tactual learners. Auditory students learn through voice and remember the content with ease. Visual learners learn better through visual images. Tactual learners learn better through hands on activities. Kinesthetic learners learn effectively using audiovisual material as well as practical assignments. They need plenty of participation in the lesson. In learning a foreign language, pronunciation is the main source of input to learn hearing. This is because some learners have a challenge of hearing a sound and repeating it. He therefore encouraged multisensory teaching. This means apart from verbal instructions, dictation, listen-and-repeat method, the teacher needs to provide visual support.

A discrepancy between how teachers perceive integration of technology and the actual implementation in the classroom. They should know that their teaching practices did not change much even with the knowledge that technology can support the content they are teaching. While teachers have adequate technology usage skills, they perceived difficulties in designing assignments using technology. Teachers also tend to think that preparing a lesson with technology use is time consuming. With such perceptions, the teachers are unlikely to integrate technology in their lessons. The survey also indicates that while access to computers and Internet were very high, some teachers said they lack confidence in using technology in classroom. These limitations can be overcome if teachers are encouraged to integrate technology through training. Altman points out that role of the teacher is to foster lively interaction with the video program because even the best book on methodology and the best teaching materials will not work if a teacher is not enthusiastic about the materials. [Altman R., 1989].

The teacher has to play different roles in the classroom at the same time. Harmer suggests three roles if the teacher is trying to get students to speak fluently.

Prompter: the teacher should help his/her students when they get lost, or cannot think of what to say next or in some other way lose the fluency the teacher expects of them. Sometimes, the best option teacher can do is to leave the students to struggle out on their own. However, the teacher may offer discrete suggestions to help the students.

Participant: teachers can participate in discussions or role-plays themselves to prompt covertly, introduce new information this will help the activity along, ensure continuing student engagement, and maintain a creative atmosphere.

Feedback provider: teachers should be aware of when and how to give feedback in speaking activities because over-correction may inhibit students and take the communicativeness out of the activity. On the other hand, positively and encouragingly correction may get students out of difficult misunderstanding. Everything depends upon teacher tact and the appropriate for the feedback provided [Harmer J., 2001, p.275/276].

In the literature review dealt with teaching English using videos being a new and challenging technique. It started by defining significance of videos and their types. And we mentioned theoretical point about teaching a foreign language through videos. In addition, it introduced the purposes of using videos in teaching English and providing some benefits of using such technique and incorporating it in teaching. Furthermore, it gave specific and detailed information about use of videos in English pointing at the fact that they are the core of this study. It was concluded by giving the advantages of using videos in teaching English.

Based on the review above it clears that using video is more beneficial and helpful than using traditional communication and audio. Referring to the findings, we can conclude that in general video is an effective teaching media especially to teach listening in English. Video is more effective than audio as teaching media. Some of the reasons for the positive perceptions included the opportunity for students to learn at their own time. Finally, the media of video has influence to the students listening skill.

we found that technology is a term that refers to a body of knowledge. Technology includes the use of materials, tools, techniques and sources of power to make life easier. In education, Technology is able to improve the teaching and learning process. The variety of media and technology that can be used to obtain information and knowledge. Teaching with technology can more effective, fun cause the teacher has many ways to create the enjoyable class, and it can make the students interesting in learning process. Teachers can be able to use the different apps or trusted online resources to enhance the traditional ways of teaching and learning and to keep students more engaged in the classroom. The application that the teacher can use like YouTube, Twitter, podcasting, Skype. Technology can help develop many practical skills, including creating presentations, learning to differentiate reliable from unreliable sources on the Internet, maintaining proper online, etiquette, and writing emails. These are very important skills that can be developed in the classroom by using technology. So, using technology not only to get more information about something but also in the education it can make the students more effective, flexible, and interesting in learning process.

In summary, video materials are a powerful tool in English language classrooms, offering an engaging and effective means of enhancing language skills. Teachers who carefully select and integrate videos into their teaching strategies can provide students

with a richer, more immersive learning experience, fostering both linguistic competence and cultural awareness.

Teachers use video for a variety of reason. Video can breathe meaning and life into nearly any lesson and make it understandable for all students. While using videos in classroom the teacher can provide a common experience for all students, generate interest and stimulate imagination because it is motivation tool in classroom. In addition to stimulate the development of critical thinking skills thus, it can develop students' speaking skills too.

Teaching with video as an aid reinforce the spoken and written language with concrete images and thus provide rich perceptual images which are the bases to learning. When video materials are used in an interrelated way, they make learning permanent. They provide for a great variety of methods. Video materials bring the outside world into the classroom and make the teacher's work efficiently.

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